

**GENDER AND LEADERSHIP ROLES
(GENDER EQUALITY AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT)**

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Abstract

Leadership has been a part of human experience since people formed groups to survive threats from the environment. Gender is an individual difference characteristic that is relevant to how people think about themselves. How people are thought about by others. How people act in various situations. Gender, therefore, is relevant to consider with regard to how it relates to leadership effectiveness.

Company leadership around the world remains unbalanced, with women accounting for less than a quarter of management positions globally. The disparity is even greater when it comes to higher-level management positions. There is no doubt that gender has had a major impact on leadership availability and fulfillment in the workplace. Though women have struggled for a long time to effect positive change with respect to hiring and promotion practices enabling women to secure leadership positions, the struggle is clearly not over. Even though the numbers are improving they are doing so slowly.

Until recently, leadership positions have predominantly been held by men and men were therefore stereotyped to be more effective leaders. Women were rarely seen in senior leadership positions leading to a lack of data on how they behave in such positions. However, current research has found a change in trend and women have become more prevalent in the workforce over the past two decades, especially in management and leadership positions.

Gender must be considered to determine how each leader can reach maximum potential and effectiveness. The present paper uses this conceptual framework of leadership to discuss how consideration of gender may affect and optimize leadership development and effectiveness.

1. Introduction

The selected topic of “Gender and leadership role” needs intense discussion because of professional, political, cultural and personal realities of the twenty-first century.

Women and men have been, are, and should be leaders.

Gender must be considered to determine how each leader can reach maximum potential and effectiveness. The present paper uses this conceptual framework of leadership to discuss how consideration of gender may affect and optimize leadership development and effectiveness. It is the goal of this project paper to lay out the issues that educators of leaders should be aware of, to achieve success for the good of the groups and individuals they have to lead.

2. Review of Literature

Morgan Stanley report: "If women ran the world, there would be no wars." It's an old stereotype, but there's something to be said for the effects of more women in leadership positions. In fact, "more gender diversity, particularly in corporate settings, can translate to increased productivity, greater innovation, better products, better decision-making, and higher employee retention and satisfaction."

LedBetter : Despite the observed benefits, however, company leadership around the world remains unbalanced, with women accounting for less than a quarter of management positions globally. The disparity is even greater when it comes to higher-level management positions. Data compiled by this research group discovered that of the 234 companies that own almost 2,000 of the world's most recognized consumer brands, only 14 of the companies had a female CEO, while nine of them had no women at all serving in executive positions or on their boards.

3. Objectives

The key elements for achieving Sustainable Development Goals, set out in the United Nations' 2030 Agenda, is to “achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls”.

Until recently, leadership positions have predominantly been held by men and men were therefore [stereotyped](#) to be more effective leaders. However, current research has found a change in trend and women have become more prevalent in the workforce over the past two decades, especially in management and leadership positions.

By integrating sustainable consumption and production (SCP) patterns into national development planning and implementation, Global citizens can make it easier and cheaper to produce goods and services with lower risks to humankind and the environment. Who are at best to do these things...the answer is women.

Creating a more inclusive culture takes time, but with cooperation from companies around the world, gender equality in upper-level management may be closer than ever and we all should find out ways to achieve this goal of “gender equality and empowering all women and girls” to fulfill Sustainable Development Goals, set out in the United Nations' 2030 Agenda.

4. What is Leadership?

- Leadership is a process and not an act or set of acts.
- Leadership is not just influence, yet it involves influencing others through the leadership. While between the leader and followers, the influence is mutual, together, they influence the environment around them in some way.
- Leadership goes beyond goals. There is a common purpose, a cause, which connects leader with followers who might have different individual goal.

5. Types of Leadership

A. Authentic Leadership

The recent authentic Leadership is about being genuine and not attempting to play a role; not acting in a manipulative way. This has evolved in the light of recent major scams and scandals, a blind race for profits and personal gains.

B. Autocratic Leadership

This type of leadership proves to be useful where close level of supervision is required. Not suitable for creative employees because morale goes down. Since they are unable to take any part in decision making, this results in job dis-satisfaction and staff turnover.

C. Transnational Leadership

The Informational leadership is a leader who is a facilitator of change occurring, when one or more persons engage with others. High level of communication exists between managers and employees and it is under the guidance of leaders that employees meet their goals and enhance productivity and efficiency.

D. Bureaucratic Leadership

This type of leadership leaves no space to explore new ways to solve issues and in fact work by book. This type of leadership is normally followed in hospitals, universities, banks and government organizations to reduce corruption and increase security.

E. Charismatic Leadership

The charismatic leader is visionary and works by infusing high amount of energy and enthusiasm in his team. This type of leader is committed to the organization and believes more in him rather than his team.

F. Participative Leadership

Participative leadership consults employees and seriously considers their ideas when making decisions.

G. Directive Leadership

Directive Leadership provides guidance about what should be done and how to do it, and maintaining standards of performance. Thus, it may be inferred that directive leadership is effective as the subordinates lack experience, has a high need for clarity or a low need of achievement.

H. Supportive Leadership

Supportive Leadership shows concern for the needs of the employees, leader is friendly and approachable. Supportive Leadership is more suitable for highly structured tasks, under bureaucratic and formal authority relationship.

I. Achievement Oriented Leadership

This type of Leadership encourages employees to perform at their highest level by setting challenging goals, emphasizing excellence and demonstrating confidence in employees' abilities.

6. Why this Objective is required to be achieved globally?

- a) One of the key elements for achieving sustainable development is the transition towards Sustainable Consumption and Production (SCP). Another key element for achieving Sustainable Development Goals, set out in the United Nations' 2030 Agenda, is to “achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls”.
- b) This goal is also regarded as indispensable to achieving sustainable development. According to UN data, 19% of women between 15 and 49 years-old say - they had suffered physical or sexual violence – or both – at their hands of their partner. Women still don't enjoy the same conditions in the workplace as men - and worldwide earn an average 24% less. (Source: Sustainability for all - United Nations and International Women's Day)

7. Relationship between Gender and various component of leadership's virtues

Let's us examine relationship between gender and various component of leadership's virtues

A. Relationship between Gender and Communication

Individuals employ different communication styles. Feminine communication has been described as more indirect, elaborate, and emotional, whereas masculine communication has been described as more direct, succinct, and instrumental. The feminine linguistic style can help to establish rapport and encourage conversation and comfortable exchange of information, but it also can be interpreted as uncertainty, tentativeness, and a lack of authority.

Stereotypically masculine characteristics (such as assertiveness and self-reliance) are often seen as components of effective leadership. Women who use a “feminine” communication style may be considered less competent than men in leadership roles. As a result, women's competence in leadership is often undervalued based on communication style. Because female leaders are not considered to be as effective communicators as male leaders, women's communication style may reinforce the stereotype that they are less competent than men in a leadership position. In contrast, when women use more “masculine” communication styles, they may be perceived as pushy or arrogant, depending on context. Similarly, men who use more “feminine” communication styles may be perceived as weak or lacking confidence.

B. Relationship between Gender and Leadership style

One of the largest moderators is the sex composition of the organization. Differences between male and female leaders in democratic and autocratic styles are significantly reduced in male-dominated groups than in female-dominated groups.

C. Relationship between Gender and Interpersonal perspective

The interpersonal perspective focuses on how leaders interact with superiors, coworkers, and subordinates. Accordingly, gender makes a difference because men and women have different types of social interactions with their male and female supervisors, peers, and subordinates, and these interactions influence outcomes.

D. Relationship between Gender and emotional Intelligence

A review of sex, gender, and emotional intelligence offers mixed findings. Some research indicates that women may have slightly higher levels of emotional intelligence compared to men.

8. Suggestions - for way forward

A. We should invest in companies who champion diversity: The business community can also have a positive impact on female equality by investing in companies that are pioneering this change. "It's time for women to start their own businesses and begin to invest in new ones that are diverse..

There are a handful of venture capitalists and private equity firms that see diversity as a priority and focus on companies with diverse executive teams as part of their investment strategy. The firm 112Capital, for instance, has invested in female-led tech companies, while the JumpFund focuses on female-led ventures in the southeastern U.S. If more firms embrace this objective, a new wave of female executives will emerge.

B. We should make the company's result public and show to the world: Improving the opportunities for female executives at your own company is one thing, but inspiring other organizations to do the same is where the real battle lies. One way to do that is by making women leaders visible. When Emily Culp, CMO of Keds, is invited to industry events, she shares her invitation with her female colleagues. She raises the visibility of her entire team by encouraging them to partake in public speaking events and activities outside of work, such as serving on a board or volunteering. She explains the value: "Real business opportunities come out of these events, but you have to be present to network."

Conclusion

The topic of gender and leadership deserves serious and thoughtful consideration and discussion because of professional, political, social, and personal realities of the twenty-first century. Science and society have come to appreciate that women and men cannot simply be classified and distinguished based on biological sex. Instead, gender is a more complex and meaningful way to understand individual differences. Every one needs to understand that how gender relates to the leadership domains of Character, Competence, Context, and Communication across the Personal, Interpersonal, Team, and Organizational levels of interaction. It is important to understand and appreciate how gender may contribute to self-perception and perception by others and that this understanding has the potential to help optimize leadership effectiveness.

Creating a more inclusive culture takes time, but with cooperation from companies around the world, gender equality in upper-level management may be closer than ever and we all should work towards this goal of achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls to fulfill Sustainable Development Goals, set out in the United Nations' 2030 Agenda.

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